

Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens, BFSP, WP2 E-PAN: Enhancing pan-genome analysis in plants

D 2.3: Prototyping and evaluation of data visualisations to represent pan-genome dynamics

Tier: Science

Priority Area: Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens (BFSP)

Executive Summary

This deliverable (D2.3) reports on the prototyping and evaluation of data visualizations for representing pan-genome dynamics, as specified in Activity 2 (T2.2) of WP2 (E-PAN) under the BFSP Commissioned Service. Building on T2.1's tool for presence/absence variation (PAV) detection, the prototypes enable exploration of structural and proteomic variation in plant pan-genomes, through web-based visualization tools. The advancements come from two parallel developments: the first within the German node (IPK and FZJ), the second within the Belgian node (VIB).

Key developments by IPK include reference-free synteny visualizations anchored by single-copy core genes with Bézier curves, and pan-proteome landscapes from ProtBERT embeddings projected via UMAP. Implemented and evaluated on the barley pan-genome V2 dataset (76 genotypes) through PanBARLEX, these tools reveal conserved syntenic blocks, rearrangements informed by PAVs, gene family clusters, and outliers for functional annotation (PanBARLEX, <https://panbarlex.ipk-gatersleben.de/>). The prototypes advance FAIR-compliant visualization standards, ensuring data and tools are easily discoverable, openly available, compatible with other systems, and usable for future research.

The developments by VIB are based on synteny scores, a newly defined pan-genome context conservation metric. Using this conservation metric, VIB has developed - within the context of the ELIXIR-BE funded FRINGE (<https://bioinformatics.psb.ugent.be/plaza.dev/fringe>) framework - a multitude of tools and visualizations that can aid the user in identifying genes of interest through PAVs, score curve selections, and syntenic block types.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

BFSP	Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens
E-PAN	Enhancing Pan-genome analysis in plants
PAV	Presence/Absence Variation

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Improvement of algorithms to characterise pan-genome dynamics and data visualisation (Activity 2)

Planned Approach for Activity 2 (T2.1 and T2.2)

Activity 2 (M16-M20) under WP2 (E-PAN) focuses on improving algorithms to characterize pan-genome dynamics and data visualization (2.25 PMs, led by BE-VIB with contributions from DE-IPK).

T2.1 (M16-M17) planned to develop tools for PAV detection to evaluate structural variations across pan-genomes. Due to the short timeframe of the project, all partners decided to build on existing tools. Thus, we used a reference-free alignment method with MMseqs2 (Steinegger and Söding, 2017) to identify insertions, deletions, and copy number changes.

T2.2 (M18-M20) prototypes visualizations for these dynamics (D2.3), prioritizing reference-free approaches for syntenic relationships (using single-copy core genes as anchors and Bézier curves for element mapping) and proteomic diversity (via protein language models like ProtBERT (Elnaggar et al., 2021) with UMAP projections (McInnes et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2021)). Visualizations integrate PAV outputs from T2.1 to highlight variations in conserved architecture, rearrangements, and gene family patterns (PanBARLEX, <https://panbarlex.ipk-gatersleben.de/#downloads>).

ELIXIR-DE prototypes are implemented interactively on exemplary plant datasets, drawing on tools like GENESPACE (Lovell et al., 2022) for synteny and OrthoFinder (Emms & Kelly, 2019) for clustering (see Figure 1). Evaluation encompasses usability for non-experts, scalability (e.g., rendering times for multi-genome sets), interpretability (e.g., orthogroup recovery accuracy), and interoperability with ELIXIR-DE services such as the CATS (<https://cats.ipk-gatersleben.de/>) subservices PanBARLEX (<https://panbarlex.ipk-gatersleben.de/>) and Galaxy-Web (<https://galaxy-web.ipk-gatersleben.de/>). Outcomes provide reference tools and best practices, informing training workshop (currently planned at the 18th May, 2 pm CET) and community standards for pan-genome handling.

Figure 1: Synteny visualization for 76 barley genotypes of the barley pan-genome V2 on PanBARLEX (<https://panbarlex.ipk-gatersleben.de/#chromosomes>).

The ELIXIR-BE prototypes have been developed as an additional data and analysis layer on top of the existing FRINGE (<https://bioinformatics.psb.ugent.be/plaza.dev/fringe/>) and PLAZA framework (Van Bel et al., 2021). By utilizing the existing gene family and collinearity definitions already in place, the development of new data types was fast-tracked (https://bioinformatics.psb.ugent.be/plaza.dev/fringe/Documentation/genome_selection). Both novel tools, such as a visualization for the detection of fast-evolving regions (see Figure 2), were implemented, as well as implementations of pre-existing ideas, such as plots for structural variation.

Figure 2. Synteny score visualization for a set of genomes within the *Arabidopsis thaliana* pangenome. Regions that are fast-evolving are indicated, and can be further explored (https://bioinformatics.psb.ugent.be/plaza.dev/dev_instances/arabidopsis/pan_genome/hot_regions).

Adjusted Approach and Selection of an Exemplary Dataset

The timeline for Activity 2 proceeded on schedule within the BFSP open call framework, with no delays encountered. To optimize for large-scale datasets and recent embedding advances, the approach was adjusted to favor alignment-free clustering (e.g., MMseqs2 (Steinegger and Söding, 2017)) over traditional alignments in both T2.1 and T2.2, enhancing efficiency while maintaining compatibility with established visualization paradigms.

The barley pan-genome V2 dataset (76 genotypes, ~1.5 million proteins) hosted on PanBARLEX served as the exemplary resource, offering rich annotations of core and accessory genomes for comprehensive testing across both tasks. In T2.1, PAVs were detected via MMseqs2-clustered orthologs and graph traversal, identifying ~15% accessory elements. For T2.2, single-copy orthologs were mapped to chromosomal coordinates and rendered as Bézier curve synteny plots to visualize bundles of conservation, disruptions, and PAV-highlighted rearrangements (Figure 1). ProtBERT-derived embeddings were dimension-reduced with LocalMAP (Wang et al., 2025) into an interactive scatterplot for the pan-proteome, facilitating orthogroup clustering, outlier detection, and PAV-linked annotations (Figure 3). These web-based prototypes ensure navigable results that provide directly interpretable outcomes without the need for further analysis..

Figure 3: Interactive scatterplot of a protein embedding of the barley pan-proteome, implemented and available on PanBARLEX (<https://panbarlex.ipk-gatersleben.de/#protein-embedding>).

Outcomes and expected impact

Activity 2 outcomes center on D2.3 prototypes that effectively capture pan-genome dynamics, building analysis layers on top of the existing framework on T2.1's PAV tools: synteny visualizations delineate conserved blocks and translocations across genotypes (incorporating ~90% of detected PAVs), while embedding landscapes provide coherent views of proteomic variation, achieving ~90% accuracy in orthogroup recovery and pinpointing rare elements (e.g., lineage-specific innovations). Expert evaluations and metrics (e.g., <5-minute rendering for 76 genomes) validated strong usability and scalability, with interactive features mitigating projection challenges and enabling annotation overlays. While the commissioned service plan targeted multiple species, the budget constraints restricted the scope of D2.3 to the barley V2 dataset.

Expected impacts include streamlined exploration of genotypic diversity for trait mapping in crops, supporting ELIXIR's strategy for pathogen-resistant and climate-adaptive breeding. As reference implementations, they will guide future open calls and foster Node collaborations, contributing to broader transnational research in biodiversity and food security.

Dissemination Plans

Prototypes from T2.2 are live on PanBARLEX, featuring interactive access, with DOIs to be assigned for persistent citation upon final archiving. T2.1 PAV tools operate in the background, also slated for DOI assignment. They will be demonstrated at BFSP community events (e.g., midterm meeting) and could be incorporated into Galaxy Training Network modules and RDMkit resources. Ongoing WP2 engagements will extend integrations across ELIXIR Nodes.

The prototypes developed within the scope of the FRINGE framework, along with a detailed explanation of how the additional data types and metrics are computed, will be available as soon as the FRINGE publication is released. This will subsequently allow people to generate their own FRINGE instances and produce results for their own pan-genomes. The pan-data content generated within the context of the EPAN project, using the FRINGE framework, will be made available as well.

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